

OPPORTUNITIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIAL ACTIVITY OF UNORGANIZED YOUTH

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Abstract. *The article will talk about the state policy on youth today. Foreign interpretation of the work carried out with private, unorganized youth. Also, the opportunities for the development of social activity of unorganized youth are described. The article will talk about the state policy on youth today, Foreign interpretation of the work carried out with private, unorganized youth. Also, the opportunities for the development of social activity of unorganized youth are described*

Keywords: *public policy on youth, youth, unorganized youth, social activism, foreign experience, problems.*

Introduction. Cinema is one of the youngest and at the same time one of the most popular arts that have a powerful impact on the hearts and minds of humanity and especially young people.

Today, cinema is one of the forms of expression of national identity, a part of national culture; therefore, a feature film has no less value than folk tales, songs, and epos, speaking as a spokesman and follower of national traditions. Each of the film's creators belongs to a certain national culture, its subculture, grew up in certain social conditions and, finally, in a geographical area characterized by its own combination of landscapes, its own color, brightness, and rhythm of natural phenomena. So, in Scandinavian films, as a rule, regardless of the storyline (it is a comedy or a drama, with a tragic or life-affirming end), the tones are dim, as if hazy, somewhat blurred. The prevailing colors are shades of brown and gray, as a result of which stereotypical images of northern landscapes arise in the imagination: low, gray sky, dark gray turbulent sea, sparse vegetation. Another feature of the "northern" cinema is the pronounced slowness of action in a film of any genre. The harsh nature of the North European countries teaches them to be cautious: they took a hasty wrong decision, started fussing, and you can pay with your life. Its features have Italian and Spanish cinema. The colors of Spanish cinema are bright and saturated, a powerful impulse comes from the screen of the thirst for life, the enjoyment of life, the sensation of life: whatever it is, with all its paradoxes and unpredictability. A sense of beauty aestheticism, and beauty is often replaced by purity. In Italy, the mastery of the interiors of houses brought to perfection, in England, cozy houses, and in Germany clean. The cinema of Latin American countries has much in common with Spanish, characterized by bright colors, the "riot of colors" of the surrounding nature and the dynamism of the plot. The same feeling of fullness of life remains, however, blue (ocean and sky), and the spirit is always preserved in a magical way physically tangible, breathtaking spatial perspective, the vast expanse of these southern countries. Features of American cinema know everything. Striking scale, the scope of the vast majority of Hollywood blockbusters. Often the film begins with a carefully calculated panoramic frame: a view from above on the mirrored skyscrapers of New York and Los Angeles. And even if you did not see an impressive panorama at the beginning of the film watch it, and a similar frame will definitely be at the end. This artistic device, albeit in a hypertrophied form, reflects the

spaciousness and power of a huge country, at least in the way that mass consciousness perceives it. “Beautiful America!” - Americans call their country. In confirmation of this, its vast expanses from hot deserts to eternal snows, worthy of admiration of people who created a powerful new state out of nothing a place where you feel light. A comfortable and comfortable life, a tolerant attitude to language mistakes and a strong accent, a sincere desire to help your neighbor all this still attracts in search of happiness of numerous immigrants who dream of becoming “real” Americans. So, America creates its image through cinema.

Research Methodology. Thus, cinema is the best intermediary for creating the image of the state. In France, when interviewing foreign tourists, the question why they came here, and not to Greece, Spain, Italy, people answered: we watched the French cinema, and now we decided to see everything with our own eyes.

In this regard, we must pay attention to the national cinema of our country. There are almost no worthy films in our national film fund dedicated to the life and work of our great scientists, cultural figures, literature and art, eminent statesmen and military leaders who were born, lived and worked on our land and made a significant contribution to the development of world civilization. People are looking forward to such films, where the history of our people will be described objectively, illuminated through expressive artistic images. Meanwhile, feature films and video films broadcast on Uzbekistan’s television are largely about the history of foreign countries, their military and political figures, as well as scientists. Today neighboring foreign countries together with leading foreign film studios create and show films all over the world about their national heroes, even about such figures who have not gained worldwide fame. This experience boosts national pride and is considered to be a powerful propaganda tool uniting the nation. We must take the initiative in broadly promoting at the international level the successes of culture and art of the people of Uzbekistan, in creating works of cinema devoted to the life and work of great scientists, cultural figures, literature and art, government leaders and military leaders who were born, lived and worked on the territory of modern Uzbekistan and made a significant contribution to the development of world civilization. We consider it important to provide funding for this work, including to create such films in conjunction with foreign film studios, with the participation of well-known directors and actors for bringing them to the world community.

Analysis and results. Lectures in the practice of teaching in higher educational institutions are one of the standard traditional forms of teaching the theoretical foundations of any academic discipline remains. There are a number of cases in the educational process, and the lecture form of teaching cannot be replaced by any of its other forms. Lecture performs the following tasks; In the modern world, cinema rightfully occupies one of the first places among other types of art, therefore it is of great importance. The art of the screen in its best works demonstrates the moral wealth of a person, the breadth of his needs and ideals, his awareness of his historical role on earth, asserts high spiritual values. In the cinema as a specific sphere, the structures of the most ancient language of mankind come to life, with the help of which they get the expression of a phenomenon of political and social history. But even more, the processes of the history of mentality are represented in this language. Cinema is undoubtedly a unique means of penetrating into the deep structures of history, and in this sense it carries out exceptional intercultural social functions. Nevertheless, cinema is not only the reality of a specific language, but also content adequately conveyed only with the help of a given language.

Conclusion. From this point of view, cinema represents a huge layer of culture, practically not used in the work of advertising specialists, as an opportunity to enter into the “taste and smell” of a given country’s culture, as well as to understand the peculiarities of nonverbal communication transmitted through emotions, gestures, clothes, customs, traditions. The film industry today is forced to adapt to new social shifts. Nowadays it is difficult to imagine the viewer and, most importantly, to make him believe in the image of a positive hero. It is important that filmmakers pay more attention to tapes that allow to bring to the surface the problems of a spiritual and moral nature, problems without understanding of which it is difficult to build relationships with the outside world, not conflicting with generally valid values and traditions, and also have the image of their state.

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